

BIR O'LCHAMLI NOCHIZIQLI KRISTALL PANJARALAR ZANJIRIDA FRENKEL-KONTOROVA MODELINI QO'LLASH.

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada bir o'lchamli nochiziqli kristall panjaralar zanjirida Frenkel–Kontorova modeli qo'llanilishi o'rganilgan. Model atomlar zanjirining periodik substrat potentsiali ta'siridagi harakatini ifodalaydi. Avvalo, tizim uchun Lagrangian funksiyasi tuzilib, u orqali harakat tenglamasi hosil qilindi. Diskret panjaraning uzluksiz chegaraga o'tish jarayoni ko'rsatildi va natijada modelning uzluksiz shakli Sine–Gordon tenglamasi ko'rinishida yozildi. Ushbu tenglamaning analitik yechimi sifatida kink tipidagi soliton yechim topildi hamda uning energiya va impuls zichliklari hisoblandi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, solitonning energiyasi va impulsi kristall panjara davri hamda solitonning tarqalish tezligiga bog'liq. Tadqiqot Frenkel–Kontorova modelining nochiziqli to'lqin hodisalarini, xususan, solitonlarning xususiyatlarini tahlil qilishda muhim nazariy asos yaratadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Bir o'lchamli nochiziqli kristall panjaralar, Frenkel-Kontorova modeli, zanjir tizimi, solitonlar, fazoviy tuzilma, energiya minimumi, kristallografik modellashtirish

Kirish. Ko'z oldimizga bir o'lchamli atomlari to'g'ri chiziq bo'ylab joylashgan

kristall zanjirini tasavvur qilaylik, kristall ichidan bitta yunalish tanlab olinib faqat shu yunalishdagi atomlar tasiri o'rganilsa shunday model hosil bo'ladi. Zarralar (atomlar) zanjirini tasvirlovchi oddiy model, ya'ni eng yaqin qo'shnilar bilan o'zaro ta'sir qiluvchi va periodik substrat potentsialiga duch keluvchi tizim. Biz shunday kristall zanjirida hosil bo'luvchi tebranishlarni tadqiq qilamiz bu tizimda hosil bo'ladigan energiya va impulsni tarqalishi o'rganamiz.

1-rasm: *Frenkel-Kontorova modeli*

Bu model dinamik diskret model sifatida taklif qilingan.

Tadqiqot metodi. Diskret nochiziqli panjaralarning dinamikasi quyidagi Lagrangian orqali tavsiflanadi:

$$L = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \left(\frac{m\dot{u}_n^2}{2} - \frac{k}{2}(u_{n+1} - u_n)^2 - U_0 \left(1 - \cos\left(\frac{2\pi u_n}{a}\right) \right) \right) \quad (1)$$

Bu funksiya Frenkel-Kontorova[1-2] modeli yoki diskret nochiziqli panjaralar modeli uchun klassik Lagrangian shaklida berilgan.

Lagrangian uch qismdan iborat:

- Kinetik energiya:

$$T = \sum_n \frac{m\dot{u}_n^2}{2} \quad (2)$$

- Elastik potensial energiya:

$$U_{el} = \sum_n \frac{k}{2}(u_{n+1} - u_n)^2 \quad (3)$$

- Periodik potensial energiya:

$$U_{per} = \sum_n U_0 \left(1 - \cos\left(\frac{2\pi u_n}{a}\right) \right) \quad (4)$$

Lagrange tenglamasi:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{u}_n} \right) - \frac{\partial L}{\partial u_n} = 0$$

Kinetik energiya hosilasi:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{u}_n} &= m\dot{u}_n \\ \frac{d}{dt}(m\dot{u}_n) &= m\ddot{u}_n \end{aligned}$$

potensial hosilasi:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial u_n} \left(\frac{k}{2}(u_{n+1} - u_n)^2 \right) &= -k(u_{n+1} - u_n) \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial u_n} \left(\frac{k}{2}(u_n - u_{n-1})^2 \right) &= k(u_{n-1} - u_n) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Yig'indini hisoblasak:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial u_n} = k(u_{n-1} - 2u_n + u_{n+1}) \quad (6)$$

Periodik potensial hosilasi:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial u_n} \left(-U_0 \left(1 - \cos\left(\frac{2\pi u_n}{a}\right) \right) \right) = -U_0 \frac{2\pi}{a} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi u_n}{a}\right) \quad (7)$$

Yuqoridagi hosilalarni hisobga olsak, harakat tenglamasi quyidagi ko'rinishga keladi:

$$m\ddot{u}_n = k(u_{n-1} - 2u_n + u_{n+1}) - \frac{2\pi U_0}{a} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi u_n}{a}\right) \quad (8)$$

Tahlil va natijalar. Bu tenglama nochiziqli diskret panjaraning dinamikasini ifodalaydi. Berilgan harakat tenglamasi diskret nochiziqli panjaralarda solitonlarning, dislokatsiyalarning va boshqa nochiziqli to'lqin hodisalarining harakatini tavsiflash uchun ishlatiladi. Bu tenglamaning maxsus yechimlarini o'rganish orqali nochiziqli to'lqin hodisalarining chuqur fizik talqinlarini topish mumkin. Uzlüksiz chegaraga o'tish uchun biz u_n funksiyasini uzlüksiz $u(x,t)$ funksiyaga yaqinlashtirishimiz kerak [8-10]. Diskret indeks n bilan bog'liq miqdorlarni uzlüksiz x o'zgaruvchiga al-mashtirish uchun quyidagi almashtirishni qo'llaymiz:

$$u_n(t) \rightarrow u(x,t), \quad x = na \quad (9)$$

Bu yerdagi a - panjaraning asosiy masofasi (lattice spacing). Diskret farqlarni uzlüksiz limitda differensial ifodalar bilan almashtiramiz:

$$u_{n+1} \approx u(x+a,t), \quad u_{n-1} \approx u(x-a,t) \quad (10)$$

Keyin, Taylor qatoriga yoyamiz:

$$u(x+a,t) = u(x,t) + au_x + \frac{a^2}{2} u_{xx} + O(a^3)$$

$$u(x-a,t) = u(x,t) - au_x + \frac{a^2}{2} u_{xx} + O(a^3)$$

Shunday qilib, diskret ikkinchi tartibli differensiya:

$$u_{n+1} - 2u_n + u_{n-1} \approx u(x+a,t) - 2u(x,t) + u(x-a,t) = a^2 u_{xx} + O(a^4) \quad (11)$$

Endi diskret harakat tenglamamiz:

$$m\ddot{u}_n = k(u_{n-1} - 2u_n + u_{n+1}) - \frac{2\pi}{a} U_0 \sin\left(\frac{2\pi u_n}{a}\right)$$

uzlüksiz limitda quyidagi ko'rinishga keladi:

$$m u_{tt} = k a^2 u_{xx} - \frac{2\pi}{a} U_0 \sin\left(\frac{2\pi u}{a}\right) \quad (12)$$

Bu tenglama Frenkel-Kontorova [1-4] modelining uzlüksiz versiyasiga mos keladi. O'lchamsiz shaklga o'tish:

Vaqtни quyidagicha almashtiramiz:

$$t \rightarrow \frac{T}{\sqrt{k/m}} \tag{13}$$

Shuningdek, u funksiyasini quyidagicha almashtiramiz:

$$u \rightarrow \frac{Ua}{2\pi} \tag{14}$$

Ushbu almashtirishlarni harakat tenglamasiga qo'llaymiz:

$$m \frac{d^2}{dt^2} \left(\frac{Ua}{2\pi} \right) = ka^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} \left(\frac{Ua}{2\pi} \right) - \frac{2\pi}{a} U_0 \sin \alpha U \tag{15}$$

Ikkinchi hosilalarni hisobga olib, quyidagicha yozamiz:

$$\frac{m}{(m/k)} \frac{d^2 U}{dT^2} = a^2 k \frac{d^2 U}{dx^2} - \frac{4\pi^2}{a^2} U_0 \sin \alpha U \tag{16}$$

Quyidagicha belgilash kiritib:

$$\alpha = \frac{2\pi^2}{a^2 k} U_0 \tag{17}$$

Oddiy lashtirgandan so'ng o'lchamsiz shakldagi tenglamani hosil qilamiz:

$$U_{TT} - a^2 U_{xx} + 2\alpha \sin \alpha U = 0 \tag{18}$$

Bu tenglama Frenkel-Kontorova modelining o'lchamsiz versiyasini ifodalaydi. Endi esa biz bu tenglamani yechish bosqichiga o'tamiz. [5-6] Sine-Gordon tenglamasining o'lchamsiz shakli quyidagicha beriladi:

$$U_{TT} - a^2 U_{xx} + 2\alpha \sin \alpha U = 0, \tag{19}$$

bu yerda

$$\alpha = \frac{2\pi^2}{a^2 k} U_0$$

Yechimni quyidagi ko'rinishda qabul qilamiz:

$$U(x,t) = f(\xi), \quad \xi = x - vt. \tag{20}$$

Hosilalarni hisoblaymiz:

$$\begin{aligned} U_T &= -vf'(\xi), \quad U_{TT} = v^2 f''(\xi) \\ U_x &= f'(\xi), \quad U_{xx} = f''(\xi) \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

Biz yuqorida asosiy funksiadan vaqt hamda koordinata bo'yicha hosila oldik bu yerda U_T -hosilada tezlik oldidadi minus ishora ta'sir qilgani uchun hosila manfiy ishoraga ega bo'ldi Ammo koordinataning hosilasi bilan bunday emas u musbat ishorani hosil qiladi .Demak bu hosilalarni asosiy tenglamaga olib borib qo'yib soddalashtirsak quyidagicha bo'ladi

Tenglamaga qo'ysak:

$$(v^2 - a^2)f'' + 2a \sin(\alpha f) f' = 0. \tag{22}$$

Birinchi integrallash natijasida:

$$\frac{1}{2}(a^2 - v^2)f'^2 = 2\alpha(1 - \cos(\alpha f)) + C \tag{23}$$

Chegaraviy shartlardan $C=0$ deb qabul qilamiz va quyidagi integralga kelamiz:

$$\frac{4\alpha}{(v^2 - a^2)}(1 - \cos(\alpha f)) = f'^2. \tag{24}$$

Bu elliptik integral bo'lib, standart tangens-giperbolik funksiya orqali yechimga ega Shundan keyin natijaviy kink soliton yechim quyidagicha yoziladi:

x

2-rasm.

$$U(x,t) = 4 \arctan \left(\exp \left(\frac{x-vt}{\lambda} \right) \right), \tag{25}$$

Bu yerda soliton kengligi

$$\lambda = \frac{1}{\sqrt{a^2 - v^2}}. \tag{26}$$

Sine-Gordon tenglamasi uchun energiya va impuls Hisoblari Berilgan Sine-Gordon tenglamasi:

$$U_{TT} - a^2 U_{XX} + 2\alpha \sin(U) U = 0. \tag{27}$$

Soliton yechimi quyidagicha:

$$U(x, t) = 4 \arctan \left(\exp \left(\frac{x - vt}{\lambda} \right) \right), \tag{28}$$

bu yerda

$$\lambda = \frac{1}{\sqrt{a^2 - v^2}}. \tag{29}$$

Hosilalarni Hisoblash Birlamchi hosilalar:

$$U_T = - \frac{4v \exp \left(\frac{x - vt}{\lambda} \right)}{\lambda \left(1 + \exp \left(2 \frac{x - vt}{\lambda} \right) \right)}, \tag{30}$$

$$U_X = \frac{4 \exp \left(\frac{x - vt}{\lambda} \right)}{\lambda \left(1 + \exp \left(2 \frac{x - vt}{\lambda} \right) \right)}.$$

Energiya va Impuls Zichliklari Energiya zichligi quyidagicha aniqlanadi:

$$\mathcal{E} = \frac{1}{2} U_T^2 + \frac{a^2}{2} U_X^2 + 2\alpha (1 - \cos(U)). \tag{31}$$

Impuls zichligi esa:

$$P = U_T U_X \tag{32}$$

To'la Energiya va Impuls To'la energiya integral orqali hisoblanadi:

$$E = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \mathcal{E} dx \tag{33}$$

Natija:

$$E = \frac{8}{\sqrt{a^2 - v^2}}. \tag{34}$$

To'la impuls:

$$P = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} P dx. \tag{35}$$

Natija:

$$P = \frac{8v}{\sqrt{a^2 - v^2}}. \quad (36)$$

Xulosa. Yuqorida hosil qilingan (35) hamda (36) munosabatlar juda muhim hulosaga olib keladi. Chunki bu munosabatlardan soliton energiasi va impulsi kristall panjara davri hamda solitonning tarqalish tezligiga bog'liq deyish mumkin. Bu esa noxiziqli kristall panjaralarda energiya va impulsning mahalliylik shaklda uzatilishi imkonini tasdiqlaydi. Shuningdek, Frenkel–Kontorova modeli[1] orqali solitonlarning kristall panjaralar ichida harakatini va ularning o'zaro ta'sirini tahlil qilish mumkinligi isbotlandi. Olingan natijalar noxiziqli kristall tizimlarda soliton dinamikasini, dislokatsiyalar harakatini hamda energiya almashinuvi jarayonlarini chuqur o'rganish uchun muhim nazariy asos yaratadi.

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